

ADDRESSING BURNOUT AND PROMOTING MENTAL WELL-BEING AMONG NURSES: STRATEGIES AND INTERVENTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE HEALTHCARE PRACTICE.

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Abstract: *This study Addressed Burnout and Promoting Mental Well-Being among Nurses: Strategies and Interventions for Sustainable Healthcare Practice. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was used for the study. Three objectives guided the study. The population of the study comprised all the 1400 Nurse in the five Health care facilities in River's state. A total of 400 Nurses representing 28.5% of the population was used as the sample size for the study. A self-structured validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Descriptive statistics involving simple percentage, bar charts, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Results showed that majority (89.07%) of the respondents had full-time work status with over 60% of the respondents having 5 to 10 years of work experience. Further analysis of data revealed that 70% of the respondent agreed that there is high burnout among nurses while 30% said there is low burnout among nurses, increased workload, inadequate staffing levels, inflexible work schedules among others are factors responsible for Burnout among Nurses., reduced workload, adequate staffing levels, flexible work schedules among others are strategies in reducing Burnout to Promoting Mental Well-being among Nurses. Based on the results, it was concluded that the burnout is still very much present with nurses working in the hospitals. It was therefore recommended among others that both the federal and state governments should employ more qualified Nurses and increase the hazard allowance of Nurse.*

1.0 Introduction

Burnout is the perfect term to describe the situation that nurse-midwives find themselves in due to the demands of their jobs (Atallah, et al., 2016). It is possible to think of burnout as a condition that arises from ongoing working stress that has not been effectively controlled. Three aspects define it: sensations of tiredness or

low energy; a more detached mental state from one's work; or negative or cynical thoughts about one's work and diminished professional effectiveness. The term "burnout" is reserved for occurrences that occur in the context of one's job and should not be used to characterize events in other spheres of one's life (Valeras, 2020).

It is concerning and a key contributing factor to nurse-midwife burnout when a nurse-midwife is required to care for an anticipated number of patients per day or each shift without any significant extrinsic incentive (Ayamolowo, 2013). For example, typical working hours for a nurse-midwife are supposed to be between 37.5 and 40 hours per week, or roughly 8 hours per shift. However, due to the unpredictability of childbirth and the fact that babies are not always born during business hours, a nurse-midwife may end up working 24 hours per shift or even up to 100 hours per week. This means that some nurse-midwives are required to work 24 hours a day in the hospital.

In a State in the southwest of Nigeria, it was reported that 22.6% of the nurse-midwives experienced high emotional exhaustion, while 47.8% reported moderate emotional exhaustion. This suggests that 70.4% of the nurse-midwives suffered from burnout to varying degrees. Furthermore, a nationwide survey conducted in the United States revealed that, of the 3.9 million (3,900,000) nurse-midwives, about 1.2 million (1,228,500) or 31.5%, had burnout, which resulted in overwhelming physical and mental exhaustions, sleep problems, depression, and feelings of dread about their jobs (Shah, et al., 2021). Nurse-midwives who experience burnout may also experience compassion fatigue, which leads to a disengagement from patient care. As a result, it seemed that nurse-midwives' burnout had negative effects on them, their families, the workplace, and the organization (Salvagioni, et al., 2017).

As any health issue that has the potential to affect mental health can also result in sudden death when left unexamined or unattended to with a long-term solution approach, burnout is not normal and when ignored overtime can lead to

the death of personnel involved and a rise in the shortage of nurse-midwives in the nation (Costa & Pinto, 2017).

According to Shah et al. (2021), mental illness is projected to be responsible for 32.4% of years spent with a handicap worldwide. It also has a large effect on companies, with depression and anxiety disorders costing US \$1 trillion in lost productivity in 2017. In May 2019, the World Health Organization officially designated burnout as an "occupational phenomenon" in the eleventh version of the International Classification of Diseases, demonstrating the increasing awareness of mental health issues in the workplace (Valeras, 2020). Additionally, there is growing recognition of the impact that mental illness has on employees who stay on the job, in addition to the direct expenses associated with absence and mental illness. Presenteeism, or reduced productivity by workers who stay at work but have health issues, is a concern that employers are becoming more aware of burnout (Salvagioni, et al., 2017). In fact, studies have shown that the economic consequences of presenteeism are greater than those of absenteeism and employer health benefits (Atallah, et al., 2016).

Considering the magnitude of the economic burden, there is a strong case to be made for investing in mental health. According to Atallah et al. (2016), for every dollar spent on increasing treatment for common mental diseases like anxiety and depression, the benefits in terms of improved health and productivity are four times greater. There are many elements in the workplace that are known to influence employees' mental health (Edet, et al., 2015). According to Atallah et al. (2016), these include unfavorable work-related circumstances such as high job demand, low job control, low workplace

social support, effort-reward imbalance, low organizational procedural justice, low organizational relational justice, organizational change, job insecurity, temporary employment status, unusual work hours, bullying, and role stress.

Further significant indicators of workers' mental health include non-work factors such as family status and social support networks (Shah, et al., 2021). Due to factors like heavy workloads, working in emotionally charged situations, and the stigma associated with seeking care, the healthcare industry, in particular, has high rates of mental illness, including burnout, stress, PTSD, anxiety, and depression (Edet et al., 2015). A few more concerns include workplace violence Shah et al. (2021). According to Shah et al. (2021) there is also evidence linking the mental health of healthcare workers to a higher risk of patient safety incidents, lower patient satisfaction, medical errors, poorer quality of care due to a lack of professionalism, patient falls, medication errors, and infections, as well as lower patient satisfaction and higher patient safety outcomes. In addition to the substantial financial expenses associated with worker turnover and reduced job output, poor mental health among healthcare professionals exacerbates labor shortages within the workforce (Edet et al., 2015).

Despite the significant cost of mental illness and poor health, the importance of good mental health and wellness is becoming more widely acknowledged and understood in terms of concepts like happiness. This approach is gaining attention internationally, as demonstrated by the 2012 United Nations High-Level Meeting on Well-being and Happiness. Health is defined by the World Health Organization as "a condition of total physical, mental, and social welfare and not

only the absence of sickness or infirmity," and this attitude fits this definition of health (Shah, et al., 2021). This review's definition of "mental health" includes both optimistic and pessimistic views of mental wellness.

Programs for mental health prevention and promotion have grown worldwide, but only 7% of them are centered on workplaces (Valeras, 2020). According to Valeras (2020), the Global Happiness Policy Report (2018) advocates for more research to assess workplace interventions that promote worker well-being and broaden the causal evidence base on work and well-being. The efficacy of treatments to avoid occupational stress in healthcare professionals was assessed in a Cochrane systematic review conducted in 2015 (Ayamolowo, 2013). However, the study was limited to research that measured work-related stress and/or burnout using validated methods. To fully comprehend the potential advantages of enhancing work settings, it is necessary to use a more comprehensive definition of mental health that encompasses a wider range of mental health outcomes, such as the psychosocial work environment and satisfaction (Valeras, 2020). Additionally, the Cochrane review excluded cross-sectional and qualitative studies that could help clarify the efficacy of interventions in different contexts and only included quantitative studies that met strict inclusion criteria: interrupted time series for organizational-level interventions, controlled before and after studies, and randomized controlled trials for individual-level interventions. In order to combat burnout and promote mental well-being among nurses, the researcher is looking into strategies and interventions for sustainable healthcare practice.

1.1 Aim of the study

This study was aimed at addressing Burnout and Promoting Mental Well-being among Nurses: Strategies and Interventions for Sustainable Healthcare Practice

1.2 Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. Determine the level of Burnout among Nurses.
2. Ascertain factors responsible for Burnout among Nurses.
3. Ascertain strategies in reducing Burnout to Promoting Mental Well-being among Nurses.

2.0 Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional survey approach was used for this investigation. The whole nursing staff at five Port Harcourt-based healthcare institutions made up the population. In the chosen healthcare institutions, there are about, 1400, according to records from 2024. Consequently, 1400 nurses comprise the research population. Out of the overall population of 1400, 400 individuals were chosen as the sample size, which represents 28.5%. A self-structured, validated instrument was used in the investigation. A and B were the two (2)

3.0 Results

Table 1 percentage of demographic data

Age	Percent
20 – 30	15.5%
31 – 40	35.3%
41 – 50	27.4%
51 and above	19.8%
Educational qualification.	
B.NSc	22.5%
B.Sc	16.1%
Type of employment	
Full time	68.5%

components that made up the instrument. While part B focused on the study's research variables, section A included the respondents' demographic data. The tool consists of 17 questionnaire items, each on a four-point Likert scale that measures agreement (A), disagreement (D), and strong disagreement (SD). With two qualified research assistants to help, the researcher self-administered the instrument. They had prior knowledge of the instrument's need and administration methods. Within an average of six minutes, the administered copies were filled out and promptly recovered. 380 of the 400 administered copies of the instrument were recovered and fully completed, indicating a 95% return rate. The mean, simple percentage, frequency, charts, and standard deviation were used to answer the study questions. The standard mean that was used was 2.5. As a result, responses to items measuring agreed and disagreed were labeled as "agreed" if the mean was 2.5 or above, and "high extent" for items measuring extent, disagreed, and "low extent" if the mean was less than 2.5.

Part time 31.5%

Years of experience

>1 15.5%
 1 – 5 37.3%
 6 – 10 27.4%
 <11 19.8%

The result in table 1 shows that 15.5% of the respondents were between the age of 20 – 30 years, 35.3% were between 31 – 40 years, 27.4% were between 41 – 50years while 19.8 & were between 51years and above, 61.4% of the respondents had B.NSc, 22.5% had B.Sc while 16.1% had PhD, 68.5% of the respondents were

full time staff while 31.5% were part time staff, 15.5% of the respondents had less than 1 year work experience, 37.3% had 1 – 5 years working experience, 27.4% had 6 – 10years working experience while 19.8% had more that 11years working experience.

Fig. 1. level of Burnout among Nurses.

Fig 1. Shows that 70% of the respondent agreed that there is high burnout among nurses while 30% said there is low burnout among nurses.

Table 2: Factors responsible for Burnout among Nurses

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	Increased workload	2.51	0.14
2	inadequate staffing levels	2.64	0.21
3	inflexible work schedules	2.84	0.18

4	Experiencing a toxic environment	3.01	0.14
5	Unfair treatment	2.87	0.28
6	Unreasonable time pressure	3.54	0.19
7	Lack of reward or recognition	2.97	0.74
	Total	2.911	0.26

Table 2 revealed mean values ranging from 2.51 to 3.54 with an average mean value of 2.991. At a criterion of 2.5, the result shows that increased

workload, inadequate staffing levels, inflexible work schedules among others are factors responsible for Burnout among Nurses.

Table 3: strategies in reducing Burnout to Promoting Mental Well-being among Nurses.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	Reduced workload	2.78	0.18
2	Adequate staffing levels	2.74	0.21
3	Flexible work schedules	3.80	0.11
4	Conducive work environment	3.85	0.14
5	Fair treatment	3.87	0.28
6	Reasonable time pressure	2.54	0.71
7	Reward or recognition for staff	2.97	0.74
	Total	3.22	0.33

Table 3 revealed mean values ranging from 2.54 to 3.84 with an average mean value of 3.22. At a criterion of 2.5, the result shows that reduced workload, adequate staffing levels, flexible work schedules among others are strategies in reducing Burnout to Promoting Mental Well-being among Nurses.

Discussion

The findings revealed high level of burnout among Nurses. This is in line with the findings of Chiara et al.. (2019) who maintained that burnout is a common phenomenon in healthcare organizations because health professionals are continually exposed to the physical and emotional needs of their patients and are involved in complex relationships with patients’ families and have long working hours and are overloaded. Also, it consists of three symptoms: emotional exhaustion, that is, the feeling of not

being able to give anything to others on an emotional level, depersonalization, such as an excessively detached attitude towards patients and low personal accomplishment such as a negative work-related self-evaluation (Chiara et al., 2019). This was corroborated by Sidhu et al (2020) that studies utilizing burnout inventories were able to expand on their findings by describing the prevalence of burnout subdomains. of those using the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), the ‘emotional exhaustion’ subscale emerged as the most frequently cited dimension of burnout, followed by ‘depersonalization’, and then ‘personal accomplishment’. As such, respondents with a high score in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, and a low score in personal accomplishments are considered severely burnt-out. The findings revealed excessive workloads,

inadequate staffing levels, inflexible work schedules as an associated factor with work burnout among nurse. This is closely related to the findings of Edward (n.d.) who remarked that burnout is linked to under-performance, low self-esteem and feelings of hopelessness and the brains of people who are chronically burnt-out show similar damage as people who have experienced trauma. Thus, burnout reduces the connectivity between different parts of the brain which can lead to decreased creativity, working memory and problem-solving skills.

The effects of burnout can be far-reaching, adversely impacting both patients and healthcare professionals (Kelsey et al., 2023). It can lead to reduced patient satisfaction, medical errors, and decreased quality of care (Rotenstein et al., 2018). It can also lead to increased absenteeism, reduced productivity, physical and mental health problems, poor social relationships, and reduced job satisfaction among healthcare professionals (Panagioti et al., 2018). While high Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) scores (regarded as the gold standard assessment) are associated with worsened performance, the relationship between burnout and job performance can be complex and multifactorial. It may depend on a variety of individual, organizational, and contextual factors (Salyers et al., 2017).

It is crucial to address burnout and promote a healthy work environment, ensuring high-quality patient care. Neither the high prevalence nor the deleterious effects of occupational burnout are contentious. Therefore, we must focus on developing effective interventions and their implementation and sustainability. Based on our experiences as healthcare professionals and researchers, no single intervention would be sufficient to deal with burnout. Hence, a multi-

pronged approach involving individual and organizational-level strategies will be most effective (Rotenstein et al., 2018).

Managing workload is a crucial factor in reducing burnout among healthcare workers (Chiara et al... 2019). Evidence from a systematic review (of randomized controlled trials and observational studies) shows that the limitation of duty hours is an effective intervention (Chiara et al... 2019). Furthermore, adequate staffing levels and flexible work schedules will be essential in reducing workload. Realistic workload and expectations with appropriate resources and training are crucial in reducing burnout and increasing engagement in the workplace (Sidhu et al., 2020).

Additionally, healthcare workers face considerable stress and pressure on the job, which can affect their physical and mental health. Individual-focused interventions, such as mindfulness, stress management, and small group discussions, can be effective in reducing burnout (Razai & Majeed, 2022). Therefore, such services, including counseling and mindfulness, should be made accessible by healthcare employers. However, they are an addition and not a substitute for occupational interventions such as ensuring adequate staffing and manageable workloads.

5.0 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that burnout is still very much experienced by nurses. However, a good number of the nurses were resilient by adopting different strategies to reduce and manage work burnout. Thus, the associated factors of burnout are multidimensional and very much present with nurses working in these hospitals. Notwithstanding, the Nurses are passionate about their job and as such are able to manage

these associated factors from crippling the service delivery in the hospitals.

5.1. Recommendations

In the light of the discoveries made in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of health institutions in Rivers State should employ more qualified and experienced nurses to ease their workload.
2. Both the State and Federal government should review the hazard allowance of nurses for a possibility of increasing it so as to assist the nurse in managing work burnout such as having enough money to eat balanced diet and so forth.

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3. The chief medical directors of the health facilities should ensure that the environmental risks are constantly reviewed for a possibility of reducing these risks so as to reduce nurse work burnout.

4. Government at both state and federal levels should endeavor to create a more enabling work environment in the hospitals.

5. Non-governmental organizations should partner with the government to provide standard and sufficient working materials.

6. There should be a periodic offer of award of excellence to outstanding nurse so as to encourage others to put up the right attitude in overcoming work burnout.

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